

Remapping Gandhi's Vision of Traditional Knowledge System

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Indian civilisation has always been built on the principle of self-sufficiency, with the village serving as the focal point of daily life. Under colonial rule, she had been subjected to social atrocities and was struggling with her economy. Most of her problems were assigned to Britishdomination. Western industrialism was an assault to the collective soul of the nation. The nationalist politics was, therefore, close to social and economic upliftment of the Indians. The Gandhian perspective on indigenous knowledge system had evolved in response to colonial milieu. The economic ideas of the nation builder were reflected in his books, editorials and addresses. Mohandas K. Gandhi recognised India's abundant resources, given her remarkable terrain, lofty mountains, strong rivers, and expansive coastline. If these resources had been fully utilised in her communities, poverty and sickness would not have occurred. To make sure that these traditional methods are still applicable in the modern world, Gandhi envisioned dynamic and adaptable approach. In the opinion of Gandhi, education is one approach to modify tradition to fit modern demands. It is possible to incorporate traditional knowledge systems into formal education, ranging from indigenous medicine and handicrafts to agricultural skills. He also believed that the *Bhagavad Gita* had given him the moral groundwork necessary to fight the British Empire without resorting to violence.

This paper explores Mohandas K. Gandhi's views and vision for an independent India through the lens of indigenous knowledge and its influence on self-reliance programmes. This paper will look at the relevance of Gandhian ideas on traditional knowledge system.

Keywords: Indian Civilization, self-sufficiency, village economy, traditional knowledge system, nation building.